

SYNTHESIS OF SOME FOUR-MEMBERED HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS.*

BY TEJENDRA NATH GHOSH AND DEBABRATA DAS-GUPTA.

By reacting dicarbethoxythioacetocarbanic acid with an aromatic amine a four-membered heterocyclic compound, with alternate carbon and nitrogen atoms, has been obtained. The constitution of this heterocyclic compound has been established by preparing some derivatives and studying their properties. This compound has been found to undergo an isomeric change due to the migration of a hydrogen atom from nitrogen to carbon.

It has been observed (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 86; 1938, 15, 89) that thioacetocarbanic acid derivatives are characterised by their pronounced reactivity towards hydrazines and diamines and as such are of considerable value for synthetic purposes. The general mechanism of these reactions is that sulphuretted hydrogen is first eliminated and then ring-closure is effected by the elimination of either alcohol or water. Dicarbethoxythioacetocarbanic acid has now been similarly found to react readily with an aromatic amine to yield a four-membered heterocyclic compound (I, $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) with alternate carbon and nitrogen atoms. The structure (I, $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) is supported by the fact that the compound is readily soluble in alkali, yields an acetyl derivative and decolourises bromine yielding a colourless tetrabromo derivative which is tentatively assigned the structure (II) (*cf.* Farooq and Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 546). The compound (I, $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) is easily decomposed by acid or alkali, the aromatic amine being one of the degradation products. With hydrazine hydrate it yields the monohydrazide (I, $R = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R_1 = \text{CONHNH}_2$). The presence of the hydrazino group has been established by the formation of benzylidene and phenylthiosemicarbazide derivatives with benzaldehyde and phenyl isothiocyanate respectively. When treated with sodium ethoxide, the compound (I, $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) yields (III). That the compound (III) does not contain any carbethoxy group has been established. The compound (III) may be regarded as a bridged pyrimidine derivative.

* Note published in *Science and Culture*, 1940, 5, 494.

When heated at $165^\circ-170^\circ$, the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) isomerises to (IV, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) due to the migration of a mobile hydrogen atom. Whereas the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) gives a deep red colouration with ferric chloride (*cf.* Frerichs and Hartwig, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, *ii*, 72, 489) and readily decolourises bromine and potassium permanganate solution, (IV, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) does not give any distinctive colouration with ferric chloride and does not decolourise bromine or potassium permanganate solution. The compound (IV, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) yields a dianilide, and is hydrolysed to the acid (IV, $\text{R}=\text{H}$; $\text{R}_1=\text{COOH}$) with alkali, which shows that the compound is more stable than (I, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$). So far as the compounds (I and IV, $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) are concerned, it appears that a relationship exists between the internal strain in the ring due to the presence of a double bond just outside the ring and the tendency of the double bond to become saturated by the migration of the mobile hydrogen atom, thus making the ring more stable (*cf.* Kon and Speight, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2727).

The above isomeric change resembles the pentad-enol system,

which has been studied extensively by Kon, Linstead and their collaborators. Reference is also made in this connection to imino-enamine system, $\text{C}(\text{H})-\text{C}=\text{N} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}=\text{C}-\text{N}(\text{H})$, studied by Ponzio and Torres (*Gazzetta*, 1929, 89, 461).

It is recognised that the closure of a four-membered heterocyclic ring from an open-chain molecule is, in general, one of the most difficult operations in ring-formation. Ingold and Piggott (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2794) obtained 1 : 3-dimethindiazine rings. Senier and Shephard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 98, 594) obtained methylene diphenylcarbamide, which is hydrolysed by boiling water. For other four-membered heterocyclic compounds with alternate carbon and nitrogen atoms, reference is made to the work of Lippmann and Regensdorfer (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2056).

The active tautomerism of the system, $>C(H)-C=S \rightleftharpoons >C=C-S(H)$, is well known and has been observed in thioketones (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 472). A compound, containing the group-

ings $(NH-CS)$ and $\begin{matrix} R \\ \searrow \\ CH-CS \\ \nearrow \\ R^1 \end{matrix}$ (where R and R^1 are strongly negative

groups), should exhibit the characteristic feature of a tautomeric body because of the presence of two mobile hydrogen atoms. The tautomeric nature of dicarbethoxythioacetocarbamic acid has been adequately borne out by the various reactions studied. From a study of its condensation products with phenylhydrazine, *o*-phenylenediamine (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), and with an aromatic amine, as described in this paper, evidence is brought forward to show that dicarbethoxythioacetocarbamic acid shows a remarkable tendency for tautomerism in a system:

the form (Y) being considered the central phase from which (X) and (Z) originate depending upon which of the two mobile hydrogen atoms tautomerises. In the above equilibrium, one particular form predominates depending upon the nature of the reactant.

EXPERIMENTAL.

N-Phenyl-*N*:*N*'-dicarbethoxyvinyleneurea (I, X = Ph ; R = R' = CO₂Et).—Aniline (7.4 g.) was added to an alcoholic solution of dicarbethoxythioacetocarbamic acid (21 g., prepared according to the method of Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, 16A, 103), when the reaction immediately commenced with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and rise in temperature. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about 2 hours,

cooled and diluted with water, when a heavy oil was obtained, which soon solidified. The solid was first washed with very dilute hydrochloric acid, then aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless shining prisms, m.p., 74-75°. (Found : C, 56.28 ; H, 5.31 ; N, 8.65. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 55.90 ; H, 4.96 ; N, 8.69 per cent). It does not dissolve in bicarbonate solution even on long standing but is readily soluble in alkali. It readily decolourises bromine water.

Bromo Derivative (II).—Bromine was slowly added to a cold acetic acid solution of the above compound. Each drop of bromine became instantly decolourised and a crystalline solid slowly came out which crystallised from absolute alcohol in colourless shining needles, m.p., 120-21°. (Found : N, 4.49 ; Br, 51.03. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_2Br_4$ requires N, 4.50 ; Br, 51.44 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali and remains unchanged when triturated with cold dilute alkali for a long time, which shows that the compound is not a hydrobromide.

N-p-Tolyl-N : N¹-dicarbethoxyvinyleneurea (I, X = *p*-tolyl ; R = CO₂Et ; R₁ = CONH-NH₂).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the previous compound. The reaction product crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless shining prisms, m.p. 61-62°. (Found : N, 8.28. $C_{15}H_{18}O_5N_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 8.33 per cent). It is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution but readily soluble in alkali.

N-Phenyl-N : N¹-(carbethoxy-carbohydrazidovinylene)-urea (I, X = Ph ; R = R₁ = CO₂Et)—An alcoholic solution of the above compound and excess of hydrazine hydrate was heated on the water-bath for about 30 minutes and kept overnight at room temperature. On dilution with water, a semi-solid mass was obtained which was next treated with dilute alkali. A very small quantity of an alkali-insoluble compound was obtained, which crystallised from alcohol in colourless slender needles, m.p., 231-32°.

The alkaline solution, on acidification, gave a solid which crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles. It melts at 171° with instantaneous formation of a solid (colourless prismatic needles), melting at 252-53° (decomp.). (Found : N, 19.19. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires N, 19.31 per cent).

The above compound reacts readily with phenyl isothiocyanate when heated in alcoholic solution to yield the *phenylthiosemicarbazide derivative* which crystallised from large quantity of alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p., 188-89° (decomp.). It is soluble in cold alkali and is easily desulphurised by yellow oxide of mercury. (Found : N, 16.28. $C_{20}H_{19}O_4N_5S$ requires N, 16.47 per cent).

Benzylidene Derivative.—An acetic acid solution of equimolecular pro-

portions of the above compound (I, X=Ph; R=CO₂Et; R₁=CO·NH·NH₂) and benzaldehyde was heated under reflux for about 15 minutes when a crystalline solid (colourless plates) came out. As it was found to be practically insoluble in alcohol, acetic acid and other solvents, it was washed several times with acetic acid and alcohol and was found to melt at 209°-10° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14·35. C₂₀H₁₈O₄N₄ requires N, 14·81 per cent).

*5-Phenyl-1:5-diazo-(o, 2, 2) bicyclo-Δ³-hexene-2:6-dione** (III, R=Ph).—Sodium (1·1 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of absolute alcohol. After the evolution of hydrogen had ceased, 15 g. of the compound (I, X=Ph; R=R₁=CO₂Et) were added to the solution and the clear solution was heated under reflux in an oil-bath for about 3 hours, when a solid was precipitated. The solution was allowed to cool and further quantity of the reaction product was obtained by dilution with water. It crystallised from alcohol (Norit), in which it is sparingly soluble, in colourless shining rectangular plates, m.p., 245-46°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 15·17. C₁₆H₈O₂N₂ requires N, 15·05 per cent). It is readily soluble in glacial acetic acid and the solution decolourises potassium permanganate solution. It does not give any anilide or any hydrazide and is unaffected by 10-15% alcoholic potash, indicating thereby that the compound does not contain any carbethoxy group. It is insoluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and also in cold dilute alkali.

It yields an unstable yellow bromo derivative, which, on treatment with water, yields an almost colourless solid. The latter compound, which contains bromine, shrinks at 130°, slowly turns dark and resinifies above 200°, and could not be obtained in a pure state.

N-Phenyl-N:N¹-dicarbethoxy-ethenylurea (IV, X=Ph; R=R₁=CO₂Et).—The above compound (I, X=Ph; R=R₁=CO₂Et, 10 g) was heated in an oil-bath at 165°-170° for about 3 hours. The pasty yellowish mass was cooled and triturated with alcohol, when a solid was obtained, which crystallised from alcohol in colourless shining rectangular plates, m.p. 168-70°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 58·88; H, 5·74; N, 9·11. C₁₅H₁₆O₂N₂ requires C, 59·21; H, 5·26; N, 9·21 per cent). It is soluble in cold dilute alkali, and in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid from which the substance is precipitated unchanged as colourless slender needles on dilution with water. It is insoluble in ether.

The above transformation can also be effected by heating the compound (I, X=Ph; R=R₁=CO₂Et) at 125°-130° in *vacuo* for about 6-7 hours,

* Nomenclature of this compound and of other compounds described in this paper has been adopted according to the system followed in "The Ring Index" by Patterson and Capell, 1940.

when the water of crystallisation is removed. A solid with a yellow tinge is slowly formed, which, on crystallisation, has been found identical with the above compound (IV, X=Ph ; R=R₁=CO₂Et) (mixed m.p.).

Dianilide.—When a mixture of aniline (2.5 g.) and the above compound (IV, X=Ph ; R=R₁=CO₂Et, 4 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 160°-165°, there was profuse evolution of alcohol and in about 15 minutes a crystalline solid came out. After washing with alcohol, the solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless, shining, rectangular plates, m.p. 236°-38°, yield 3 g. (Found : N, 14.26. C₂₃H₁₈O₂N₄ requires N, 14.07 per cent). It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in cold dilute alkali.

N-Phenyl-N : N'-carboxyethenylurea (IV, X=Ph ; R=H ; R₁=CO₂H).—A solution of the above compound (IV, X=Ph ; R=R₁=CO₂Et, 6 g.) in 10% alcoholic potash was heated under reflux on the water-bath for about 8 hours. Alcohol was distilled under reduced pressure and the solid was dissolved in water, filtered from any suspended impurities and just acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated solid was purified by dissolving in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and acidification with acetic acid. It was crystallised from alcohol in almost colourless rectangular plates. It turns brown on heating and does not melt even at 300°, yield 0.8 g. (Found : N, 13.29. C₁₀H₈O₂N₂ requires N, 13.72 per cent).

The authors' thanks are due to Professor P. C. Guha for his kind interest in this investigation.

DEPARTMENT OF PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received October 31, 1941.